

Exploiting Data Centres and Local Energy Communities Synergies for Market Participation

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Abstract—The evolving energy landscape has propelled energy communities to the forefront of modern energy management. However, existing research has yet to explore the potential synergies between data centres and energy communities, necessitating an assessment on their collective capabilities for cost efficiency, waste heat optimisation, and market participation. This paper presents a mixed integer linear programming model to assess the collaborative performance of energy communities, data centres and energy markets. The evaluation focuses on the efficient use of waste heat and the flexibility of job scheduling while minimising system energy costs and maintaining quality of service requirements for data centres. Our results, based on realistic profiles of an energy community and a data centre, showcase significant benefits of these synergies, with a 38% reduction in operating costs and an 87% decrease in heat demand.

Index Terms—Data Centres, Energy Communities, Synergies

I. INTRODUCTION

THE energy landscape is undergoing a major transformation, marked by an increasing emphasis on sustainability and renewable energy sources. Energy communities are gaining popularity as a means of enabling local members to pool resources and collectively manage energy production and consumption [1]. At the same time, and as we move into the future, the growing use of artificial intelligence and other computing services is leading to a rising demand for enhanced computing capabilities [2]. The synergies between renewable energy, efficient computing capabilities, and the emergence of Local Energy Communities (LECs) are of paramount importance in addressing the evolving energy needs of our society.

In the realm of Data Centre (DtC) resource optimisation, authors in [3] underscore the importance of optimising resource consumption, drawing from a comprehensive five-year study of the Titan System. Reference [4] explores Internet DtCs' potential as energy prosumers, emphasising their flexibility in integrated electricity-heat systems, contributing to enhanced energy efficiency and renewable energy integration. Addressing thermal challenges, one research effort [5] recognises the significance of thermal management in the IT industry's pursuit of sustainable practices within DtCs. Additionally, an innovative approach [6] envisions DtCs as distributed nodes

providing waste heat for other building heating needs, thereby reducing overall energy consumption, showcasing adaptability and resourcefulness. Furthermore, a study [7] delves into the application of waste heat from DtCs in vertical farming, highlighting opportunities to reuse waste heat, aligning with the trend toward resource optimisation and sustainable practices in the DtC industry.

In light of these developments, LECs play a pivotal role in the energy landscape, with potential for leveraging DtCs' waste heat and flexibility in energy markets. Notably, the need for innovative sources of heating and cooling within LECs is a recurring theme, as highlighted by [8]. This study underscores the necessity for further exploration of innovative community-based initiatives. Besides, the importance of waste heat recovery and its integration with renewable energy sources to achieve sustainability goals has been consistently emphasised in research [9]. These findings collectively highlight the pressing requirement for Energy Optimization Assessments (EOAs) and standardised energy metrics to ensure the long-term sustainability and efficiency of modern energy systems. While innovative EOA have been proposed to potentially reduce costs and enhance grid flexibility [10], there is a lack of evidence regarding the contribution of DtCs to this endeavour when integrated with LECs.

The synergies between DtCs and LECs has been analysed through coordinated building heat systems and electric vehicle charging [11] and demand response programs [12], showing huge potential for efficiency increase. In addition, DtCs have the potential of providing market services without jeopardising their Quality of Service (QoS) requirements using approaches such as dynamic voltage and frequency scaling, job preemption, and hardware power capping [13]. Nevertheless, despite previous efforts, there is a research gap regarding how LECs, DtCs, and energy markets interact and benefit each other. Existing research mostly looks at them separately, missing out on potential collaboration benefits.

The main contribution of this paper is an evaluation of the value of integrating LECs and DtCs for market participation focusing on the waste heat and job scheduling flexibility. This paper proposes a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model for this assessment which minimise the total energy cost. DtC's QoS requirements are included using Big-M method.

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The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section II describes the LEC and DtC model. Then, Section III presents a Case Study based on realistic datasets for energy patterns and jobs duration. Lastly, Section IV concludes the paper.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The LEC comprises households with photovoltaic panels, flexible electricity consumption, and Electric Vehicles (EVs). A battery and a small wind generator are the shared LEC's resources. For heating, a shared Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system is employed, while private HVAC systems provide cooling. The synergies between DtCs and LECs can be investigated using an EOA module which oversees their joint energy and heat needs. This integration is especially promising for urban scale with industrial technological hubs, given regulatory distance limits that allow connections to LEC shared resources. Fig. 1 illustrates the EOA module for LECs and DtCs.

A. Data Centre model

In this section, we present a high-level model of the DtC, focusing on total computing power and QoS requirements. The DtC operates with a baseline power determined by the job workload, denoted as P_t^{wkl} . To enhance flexibility, the DtC can temporarily pause certain jobs and resume them during subsequent time periods [14]. Let p_t^{SB} be the running power of the jobs paused at time t over a set of periods Ω_t , p_t^{RE} is the resuming power, μ_t is the mean duration of the jobs running, and z_t^{DtC} is a binary variable indicating the pausing action. The extra consumption resulting from the auxiliary operations to pause and resume the jobs is modelled by a positive constant $K^S > 1$.

$$p_t^{e,d} = P_t^{wkl} - p_t^{SB} + p_t^{RE} K^S \quad \forall t \quad (1a)$$

$$0 \leq p_t^{e,d} \leq P^{DtC} \quad \forall t \quad (1b)$$

$$0 \leq p_t^{SB} \leq P_t^{wkl} z_t^{DtC} \quad \forall t \quad (1c)$$

$$0 \leq p_t^{RE} \leq P^{DtC} (1 - z_t^{DtC}) \quad \forall t \quad (1d)$$

$$d_{t,t'} = \begin{cases} \frac{t'-t}{\mu_t} & \text{if } \sum_{\tau=0}^{t'} P_\tau^{RE} \leq \sum_{\tau=0}^t P_\tau^{SB} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \forall t, t' > t \quad (1e)$$

$$d_{t,t'} \leq K^{DELAY} \quad \forall t, t' > t \quad (1f)$$

Fig. 1. General overview of the proposed EOA module for the assessment of the synergies of LECs, DtCs and Energy Markets.

$$\sum_{\tau=0}^t (p_\tau^{RE} - p_\tau^{SB}) \leq 0 \quad \forall t \quad (1g)$$

$$\sum_{\tau=0}^{|\Omega_t|} (p_\tau^{RE} - p_\tau^{SB}) = 0 \quad (1h)$$

$$q_t^{DtC} = C p_t^{e,d} + C^{MIN} \quad \forall t \quad (1i)$$

The DtC demand $p_t^{e,d}$ is modelled by (1a), which must not exceed the DtC rating P^{DtC} as (1b) states. Power being paused p_t^{SB} cannot be higher than the workload P_t^{wkl} at time t , while the re-starting power p_t^{RE} cannot be higher than the capacity of the DtC P^{DtC} , as (1c) and (1d) respectively enforce. The variable $d_{t,t'}$, computed in (1e), signifies the cumulative delay experienced by jobs that are paused at time t up to t' . It serves as a cumulative delay counter for the jobs paused at time t until the resumption of the job. However, this constraint cannot be directly solved by commercial solvers, needing a reformulation using the Big-M method, as detailed in Annex A. K^{DELAY} is defined as the maximum allowed delay to ensure QoS requirements in (1f). Equation (1g) ensures that the DtC must have previously experienced a power reduction before power is being resumed, and (1h) enforce that all the paused power must be resumed to completion within the optimisation horizon. The heat generated by the DtC in its operation q_t^{DtC} is modelled in (1i) as a linear relationship C with the power consumed $p_t^{e,d}$ plus a fixed term C^{MIN} [4].

The heat recovery system, illustrated in Fig. 2, use an evaporator to extract the heat from the DtC. After that, the heat exchanger channels a portion of this energy to a heat upgrading system, denoted as q_t^{TR} with efficiency η^{TR} , while releasing the surplus q_t^{EXT} into the surroundings. Thus $q_t^{TR} = q_t^{DtC} \eta^{TR}$. This heat upgrading is crucial due to the low-grade nature of the heat produced by the DtC, which might fall short of meeting all the heating demands within the LEC. If that is the case, the system employs a power input p_t^A to generate supplemental heat for the LEC with efficiency η^A .

B. Energy Community Model

The power flowing among the different elements is depicted in Fig. 3. Power can be bought from $p_t^{r,e}$ or sold to $p_t^{e,r}$ the retailer at prices λ_t^{DA} and λ_t^{PPA} , respectively. DtC can also benefits from its participation in automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve (aFRR) markets by providing upward reserves at price λ_t^{aFRR} pausing its jobs. The EOA module receives power $p_t^{g,e}$, $p_t^{s,e}$, $p_{h,t}^{\eta,e}$ from the wind turbine, the storage and,

Fig. 2. General overview of the Heat Recovery System. An evaporator draws heat q_t^{DtC} from the DtC, while an exchanger and a posterior heat upgrading system transfer the heat $q_{h,t}^{HE}$ to the set of households $h \in \Omega_h$.

Fig. 3. General overview of the proposed EOA for the joint operation of LECs and DtCs. Solid lines represent electric energy flows, while dashed lines represent heat transfer.

the households $h \in \Omega_h$, and delivers power $p_t^{e,s}$, $p_t^{e,d}$, $p_t^{e,\eta}$ to the shared storage, the DtC and, the households, respectively. Besides, each household optimises their flexible demand $p_{h,t}^{\eta,f}$ and their EVs $p_{h,t}^{\eta,v}$ considering the self-generation $p_{h,t}^{g,\eta}$ and the injection of the vehicle-to-house $p_{h,t}^{v,\eta}$. For the sake of simplicity, (2) seeks to minimise the global objective of the LEC, minimising the total cost of energy provision.

$$\min_{vars} \sum_t (\lambda_t^{DA} p_t^{r,e} - \lambda_t^{PPA} p_t^{e,r} - \lambda_t^{aFRR} p_t^{sB}) \quad (2a)$$

Subject to,

$$p_t^{g,e} + p_t^{s,e} + p_t^{r,e} + \sum_h p_{h,t}^{\eta,e} = p_t^{e,r} + p_t^{e,s} + p_t^{e,d} + \sum_h p_{h,t}^{e,\eta} \quad \forall t \quad (2b)$$

$$p_{h,t}^{\eta,e} + p_{h,t}^{\eta,v} + p_{h,t}^{\eta,f} = p_{h,t}^{e,\eta} + p_{h,t}^{v,\eta} + p_{h,t}^{p,\eta} \quad \forall t, \forall h \quad (2c)$$

$$p_{h,t}^{\eta,f} = P_{h,t}^{sch} + p_{h,t}^u - p_{h,t}^d \quad \forall h, \forall t \quad (2d)$$

$$\sum_t (p_{h,t}^u - p_{h,t}^d) = 0 \quad \forall h \quad (2e)$$

$$p_{h,t}^{\eta,v} \leq P_h^{EV} z_{h,t}^{ev} \quad p_{h,t}^{v,\eta} \leq P_h^{EV} (1 - z_{h,t}^{ev}) \quad \forall h, \forall t \quad (2f)$$

$$soc_{h,t} = soc_{h,t-1} + (p_{h,t}^{\eta,v} \eta_{h,t}^{CH} - p_{h,t}^{v,\eta} / \eta_{h,t}^{DIS}) \Delta t - P_{h,t}^{DRIVE} \Delta t \quad \forall h, \forall t \quad (2g)$$

$$p_{h,t}^{\eta,v} = p_{h,t}^{v,\eta} = 0 \quad \forall t \notin [t^{DEP}, t^{ARR}] \quad (2h)$$

$$\underline{SOC}_h \leq soc_{h,t} \leq \overline{SOC}_h \quad \forall h, \forall t \quad (2i)$$

$$q_{h,t}^{HE} \leq Q_h^{HE}, \quad 0 \leq p_{h,t}^{CO} \leq P_h^{CO} \quad \forall h, \forall t \quad (2j)$$

$$\tau_{h,t} = \tau_{h,t-1} + \frac{\Delta t}{R_h C_h} (\tau_{h,t}^{out} - \tau_{h,t-1}) + \frac{\Delta t}{C_h} (q_{h,t}^{HE} - p_{h,t}^{CO} \eta_{h,t}^{CO}) \quad \forall h, \forall t \quad (2k)$$

$$\tau_h^{MIN} \leq \tau_{h,t} \leq \tau_h^{MAX} \quad \forall h, \forall t \quad (2l)$$

$$p_t^{s,e} \leq z_t^{BAT} P^{BAT}, \quad p_t^{e,s} \leq (1 - z_t^{BAT}) P^{BAT} \quad \forall t \quad (2m)$$

$$soc_t = soc_{t-1} + (p_t^{e,s} \eta^{CH} - p_t^{s,e} / \eta^{DIS}) \Delta t \quad \forall t \quad (2n)$$

$$\underline{SOC} \leq soc_t \leq \overline{SOC} \quad \forall t \quad (2o)$$

$$q_t^{DtC} \eta^{TR} + p_t^A \eta^A = \sum_h q_{h,t}^{HE} + q_t^{EXT} \quad \forall t \quad (2p)$$

$$(1a) - (1i) \quad (2q)$$

Equation (2b) defines the energy balance of the EOA module, while (2c) computes the balance for each household. The household power consumption $p_{h,t}^{\eta,f}$ is modelled as a flexible demand with lower and upper bounds $\underline{P}_{h,t} \leq p_{h,t}^{\eta,f} \leq \overline{P}_{h,t}$, which comprises a baseline $P_{h,t}^{sch}$ modified in upward $p_{h,t}^u$ and downward $p_{h,t}^d$ directions by (2d). The total consumption throughout the optimization horizon is enforced by (2e). The charging $p_{h,t}^{\eta,v}$ and discharging $p_{h,t}^{v,\eta}$ power of the EV is set to zero by (2h) if t is lower than the arrival time t^{ARR} or higher than the departure time t^{DEP} . Considering P_h^{EV} as the rating of the EV charger, simultaneous charging and discharging is restricted by (2f) using binary variable $z_{h,t}^{ev}$. The State of Charge (SOC) of each household's EV depends on the charging and discharging powers and on the power needed for driving purposes $P_{h,t}^{DRIVE}$ by (2g). SOC limits $\underline{SOC}_h, \overline{SOC}_h$ are set by (2i). Maximum heating Q_h^{HE} and cooling transfer P_h^{CO} for each household are in (2j), while temperature $\tau_{h,t}$ constraints are defined in (2k) and (2l) based on the thermal resistances C_h and R_h and outdoors temperature $\tau_{h,t}^{out}$ using a first-order linear model. Heating power $q_{h,t}^{HE}$ is obtained from the shared heating system, while $p_{h,t}^{CO}$ is used to drive cooling system with efficiency η_h^{CO} . LEC shared battery is managed from (2m) to (2o), considering charging and discharging efficiencies η^{CH} and η^{DIS} , a converter rating P^{BAT} , and SOC limits \underline{SOC} and \overline{SOC} . Simultaneous charging and discharging for EVs and the shared LEC battery is prohibited by binaries $z_{h,t}^{ev}$ and z_t^{BAT} , respectively. The heat balance of the recovery system is described by (2p), for a household heating demand $\sum_h q_{h,t}^{HE}$. Lastly, (2q) represents the DtC model.

III. CASE STUDY AND SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, a case study based on realistic LEC [15] and DtC [3] information is presented. The workload DtC information is directly obtained from Oak Ride National Laboratory [16]. The LEC has 10 households with consumptions ranging between 3 and 10 kW, photovoltaic panels of similar size and, one EV per household. Each EV typically travels between 50 and 100 kilometres per day, consuming 15 to 20 kWh per 100 km. The EOA module optimise the overall energy costs as stated by (2a). The assessment evaluates the value of the synergies between DtCs and LECs, also showing the impact of the number of households included in the system. Simulations were performed using Python 3.9.2 in PYOMO and solved by Gurobi 10.0.1 on an Apple M1 with 16 GB of RAM. The assessment problem has 16,597 constraints, 2,887 variables and, 348 binaries for each day of simulation with hourly resolution. The solving time for a one-day simulation is 9.92 s, while for a 15-day simulation it is 288.9 s.

A. Synergies between LECs and DtCs

This section showcases the synergies between LECs and DtCs regarding waste heat and optimal market participation. Fig. 4 depicts the energy balance of the LEC for a typical operation day with low computational requirements. Still for an LEC of 10 households the DtC draw a significant portion

of the energy, as presented in Fig. 4 (a) with purple bars. Nevertheless, this feature enables covering the heating needs of the households primarily based on the waste heat recovery. This is shown in Fig. 4 (b) with yellow bars, showing that there is no need of driving the HVAC p_t^A .

A detailed view of the final consumption $p_t^{e,d}$ of the DtC, original workloads P_t^{wkl} , heat generated q_t^{DtC} and pausing p_t^{SB} and re-starting powers p_t^{RE} is depicted in Fig. 5 (a) for the day under study. As a result, the delay matrix for the preempted jobs is shown in Fig. 5 (b), showing the increase in $d_{t,t'}$ when jobs are being paused in two consecutive periods between 7:00 and 9:00. The delay for this case study was required to be less than 25% of the original work duration. The vertical and horizontal axis represent pausing t and re-starting t' times while the colour indicates the magnitude of the delay $d_{t,t'}$. Given the duration of the workload μ_t , and in order to meet QoS requirements, the paused power is resumed a maximum of two hours after pausing for this specific day.

B. Long run assessment

Using one year of data split into 24 simulations of 15 days each, the long-run performance of the coupling is evaluated in Table I. The Thermal Coupling (TC) + Job Pausing (JP) + aFRR scenario showcases a 37.88% reduction in operational costs compared to the No Coupling (NC) scenario. However, this cost-effectiveness does not extend proportionally to other metrics. For instance, the energy required from the retailer is only reduced by 5.81%, 6.61% and, 4.14% if we compare NC scenario to TC, TC+JP and TC+JP+aFRR, respectively. Additionally, although renewable energy production remains constant across all scenarios, the utilization of this energy varies. The auto consumption ratio stays steady at around 35%, and the additional heating requirements $p_t^A \eta^A$ were reduced by 6.98%, 10.58% and 7.85% compared to the rest of the scenarios. These strategies minimise wastage and enhance heat reuse, aligning with sustainable energy practices, while the percentage of waste heat reuse is around 87% for the last three scenarios. This showcase the potential of the DtC to provide heating to the households, reducing the need for additional

Fig. 4. Energy (a) and Heat (b) balance of the EOA of the LEC. Negative values represent energy imports while positive values are exports.

Fig. 5. DtC Energy consumption (a) and delay matrix (b) for a day of operation with low computational requirements. Vertical axis represents the pausing time t , while the horizontal axis representing the re-starting time t' .

TABLE I
LONG RUN ANALYSIS. SCENARIOS ARE NC: NO COUPLING, TC:
THERMAL COUPLING, JP: JOB PAUSING AND aFRR PARTICIPATION.

	NC	TC	TC + JP	TC + JP + aFRR
Op. Costs (k€)	95,136.47	89,771.18	88,849.72	59,103.19
Renewable Gen. (MWh)	300.62	300.62	300.62	300.62
Retailer's Energy (MWh)	576.52	543.03	543.17	552.67
AC Ratio (%)	34.27%	35.63%	35.63%	35.23%
Data Centre RE Consumption (%)	33.30%	28.21%	27.71%	27.97%
Average Job Delay (%)	0.00%	0.00%	18.62%	15.86%
Heating (MWh)	118.69	110.40	106.13	109.37
Power to HVAC (MWh)	118.69	15.79	15.67	15.76
Heat recovery ratio (%)	0.00%	87.49%	87.13%	87.41%

heating sources. Nevertheless, the increase in heat recovery ratio is driven more by the job pausing strategy than market participation.

C. Impact of the number of households

A sensitivity analysis has been performed to examine the impact of varying the number of households over a span of 10 days. Fig. 6 shows the impact of the number of connected households on the average job delay, the percentage of renewable used by DtC R_{RE}^{DTTC} , the ratio of heat recovered by households R_{HE} and the operational cost per household. This is investigated through the ratio of the LEC net demand $\sum_{h,t} (p_{h,t}^{e,\eta} - p_{h,t}^{\eta,e})$ over the DtC demand $\sum_t p_t^{e,d}$. The QoS remains stable and under the maximum requirement K^{DELAY} for this case study regardless of the number of households introduced into the LEC. Furthermore, the DtC can meet its energy demands by utilising surplus energy from households equivalent of its 60% demand. It is important to clarify that this does not indicate an exclusive reliance on renewable sources, as market trading with the retailer can occur. The cost per household is reduced as their number increases, showing a

42.85% reduction compared to the case with 5 households. However, the ratio R_{HE} also decreases with the number of households, due to the increasing needs for heating, which can be also covered by renewable surplus of each household.

Fig. 6. Impact of the ratio of the EC over the DtC demand on the QoS (blue), the percentage of renewable usage in the DtC (yellow), the ratio of heat recovery (green) and the cost per household (purple). From left to right, the number of households are 5, 10, 20, 40, 80, 100.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper undertakes an assessment of the value of the synergies among LECs, DtCs, and energy markets, exploring the potential savings regarding energy cost, waste heat reuse and job scheduling flexibility. A MILP model is used to evaluate the joint performance of LECs, DtCs, and energy markets, using the Big-M method to model the QoS requirement of the DtC. The case study results show substantial benefits, including potential reductions in operating costs, up to 38% reduction in heat demand when these synergies are exploited. Introducing job pausing contribute to better adapt to renewable variability, but it will reduce DtC's QoS. The trade-off between QoS and energy system benefits must be carefully considered, since the DtC flexibility obtains more benefits if used for market participation. In addition, up to 43% reduction in individualised operational costs can be obtained if the size of the LEC increases from 5 to 100 households. These findings underscore the potential of combining LECs and DtCs to address modern energy management challenges. Future work will investigate possible formulations of online energy management systems for joint optimisation of DtCs and LECs.

APPENDIX A

REFORMULATION OF JOB DELAY COMPUTATION

The job delay $d_{t,t'}$ is computed as $(t' - t)/\mu_t$ if and only if $\sum_{\tau=0}^{t'} P_{\tau}^{RE} \leq \sum_{\tau=0}^t P_{\tau}^{SB}$, else $d_{t,t'} = 0$. This restriction cannot be directly solved by commercial solvers. In order to do so, the Big-M method is applied, and this condition is reformulated as follows,

$$\sum_{\tau=0}^{t'} P_{\tau}^{RE} - \sum_{\tau=0}^t P_{\tau}^{SB} \leq M(1 - \delta_{t,t'}) \quad \forall t, \forall t' > t \quad (3a)$$

$$\sum_{\tau=0}^{t'} P_{\tau}^{RE} - \sum_{\tau=0}^t P_{\tau}^{SB} \geq -M\delta_{t,t'} \quad \forall t, \forall t' > t \quad (3b)$$

$$d_{t,t'} \delta_{t,t'} \leq K^{DELAY} \quad \forall t, \forall t' > t \quad (3c)$$

with M being a large enough parameter, set to 10^4 for this case, and $\delta_{t,t'}$ being a binary variable indicating the way $d_{t,t'}$ is computed.

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